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To,
Prof. Robert L. Goldstone
Executive Editor, Cognitive Science
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Dear Prof. Goldstone,

We have submitted our manuscript entitled '*Higher Dimensional Algebraic Study of Brain Functions*' through Cognitive Science journal's on-line manuscript submission system. Please consider our manuscript for publication in Cognitive Science journal. Our manuscript, to the best of our knowledge, is the first paper to show that higher dimensional algebra provides a better framework for brain theory (compared to set-theoretic elementism). We hope you will find the manuscript suitable for publication in your esteemed Cognitive Science journal.

The following may be considered for reviewing the manuscript since they have worked on subject matters related to the core themes of the manuscript.

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Kindly acknowledge the receipt of the manuscript.

Thanking you,

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Higher Dimensional Algebraic Study of Brain Functions

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ABSTRACT

Recognizing the limitations of element-wise set-theoretic constructions in accommodating contextual effects in perception, neuroscientists are trying to move beyond elementism. Mathematicians also recognized the shortcomings of 0-dimensional elementism in modelling geometry, which led to the development of higher dimensional algebra. Here we show that higher dimensional algebra meets some of the demands of cognitive neuroscience data and hence may become indispensable in implementing the paradigm shift from acontextual models such as the feature list model of percept and concept to empirically valid models. Drawing upon the experience of higher dimensional algebra, we distil higher dimensional models of percept, concept, emotion, memory, and neural information from experimental data. These studies brought to light a number of parallels between the methods of mathematics and the workings of the brain, which led us to put forward higher dimensional algebra that provides a mathematical model of mathematical practice as a model of the brain.

INTRODUCTION

Substantial progress has been made in elucidating how brain transforms physical stimuli into perceptual experiences, but much remains to be done (Albright et al., 2000). Contextual nature of perception, binding problem, and the relation between perceptual experiences and conceptual knowledge are some of the major outstanding problems (Goldstone & Barsalou, 1998; Roskies, 1999; Albright & Stoner, 2002). We need concrete models of percept and concept in order to scientifically address these problems. Currently percepts are modelled as feature collections. For example, percept = {shape, motion, color}. This feature list model is fundamentally flawed. In view of the contextual nature of visual perception, features cannot be modelled as elements of a set. Context is that which is left unaccounted for when we reduce a richly structured object to a collection of structure-less elements. Approximating features as elements and modelling percept as a discrete set creates two further intractable problems with respect to the binding problem because of the two mutually contradictory properties of abstract sets. When looked from outside elements of a set cannot be distinguished from one another, while elements have zero internal cohesion inside abstract sets (Lawvere, 1994). Thus, either there can be no binding problem –the problem of how features are bound together into a cohesive percept– because of the infinite cohesion of set. Or, if we somehow append binding problem to this model, there exists no glue within an abstract set that can bind one element to another to give rise to cohesive perception.

Concepts are also modelled as feature lists. To illustrate, face = {eyes, nose, mouth}. But feature lists do not exhaust the knowledge content of concepts: “just listing features does not go far enough in specifying the knowledge represented in a concept. People also know something about the relations between the features...” (Smith & Medin, 1981, p. 83). Ignoring these, we may work within the framework of feature list model and ask ‘how do we acquire conceptual knowledge?’ The standard answer is concept is an average of perceptual

experiences, a prototype. But ‘prototypes’ as thus defined are incompatible with the compositional nature of concepts (Fodor & Lepore, 1996; Fodor, 1998). Moving on, ‘how does knowledge structure perception?’ (Miller, 1999). Modelling perception as a sum of external sensation and internal prototype implies that percept is computed using a bit-wise measure (e.g. hamming distance) ignoring the contextual essences of percepts and concepts (Hertz, Krogh & Palmer, 1991). This schism between theory and data is hindering the progress of neuroscience. We need a theoretical framework, which can provide a cohesive account of various brain functions such as conscious perception, conceptual thinking, and emotional feelings. Towards this end, we examine the genesis of feature list model with the hope that a pedantic diagnosis may suggest a prescription.

In the process of developing a scientific account of various phenomenon and processes we, the scientists, begin with objectification, and represent the objects of scientific discourse as sets. Calculations and deductions are carried out using symbol string manipulations, i.e., equations. The feature list model is an immediate consequence of these basic well-tested methods of science (Figure 1). We treat percept as an object and represent it as a collection of features, i.e., a set and write down an equation: $\text{percept} = \{\text{color, texture, size}\}$ to do calculations. And yet we find the consequences have been to give unsatisfactory models of empirical data. This immediately raises the following question. Is pursuit of science invariably a reduction of complex objects of scientific discourse to sets and eventually to equations written along a line (Brown, 1992)?

-FIGURE 1-

Einstein, in discussing the importance of the theory of knowledge, has written: “Concepts which have proved useful for ordering things easily assume so great an authority over us, that we forget their terrestrial origin and accept them as unalterable facts. They then become

labelled as ‘conceptual necessities’, ‘a priori situations’, etc. The road of scientific progress is frequently blocked for long periods by such errors. It is therefore not just an idle game to exercise our ability to analyse familiar concepts, and to demonstrate the conditions on which their justification and usefulness depend, and the way in which these developed, little by little...” In this spirit, Brown has questioned the rationale behind confining to and the adequacy of structure-less sets and equations written along a line in modelling geometry algebraically, which led to the development of a philosophically profound and methodologically concrete discipline known as higher dimensional algebra (Brown, 1982, 1992; Baez, 1997, 2001; Brown & Porter, 2002a). Unlike set theory, where we reduce richly structured objects to collections of structure-less elements, higher dimensional algebra builds algebraic structures with geometric features, in order to better model geometry (Brown & Spencer, 1976; Brown & Higgins, 1981; Brown & Mosa, 1999). Unaware of these developments, which has also been called ‘post-modern algebra’, and which are liberating science from the confines of “lineland”, philosophers tend to treat “linear thinking” evident in mathematician’s equations, computer scientist’s Turing tape, and biologist’s DNA code as an inviolable law of human nature to which we have to resign (Draaisma, 2001).

The core theme of higher dimensional algebra is ‘composition’ whose relevance for cognitive neuroscience can be readily discerned by noting that many outstanding questions such as ‘how does brain integrate tactile information about an object that is fragmented by peripheral sensors?’, ‘how does brain put sensory features together into a cohesive percept?’, and ‘how perceptual experiences are put together to give rise to conceptual knowledge?’ are questions of ‘composition’. In the present paper we show that higher dimensional algebra resonates with some of the demands of cognitive neuroscience data and as such deserves the serious consideration of neuroscientists in search of better alternatives to such paradigms as

feature list, and will hopefully and eventually suggest a more comprehensive theory of brain functions than possible in the current framework.

HIGHER DIMENSIONAL ALGEBRA AND THE BRAIN

Higher dimensional algebra is an algebraic framework where composition is defined under geometric conditions, unlike the more familiar addition or multiplication. To see this, consider a country. A country can be modelled as a set of cities and these cities can be represented as points. The paths connecting cities can be represented as line segments. We can think of lines as collections of points but that is not very useful. If we model line segments as numbers, then we can use numbers to calculate the distance travelled while going from one city to another via an intermediary city. In the process we use operations such as addition and calculate using equations: $500 \text{ km} + 200 \text{ km} = 700 \text{ km}$. This algebraic machinery –sets and equations– captures quite a bit of geometry but much is left out (Figure 2). For example, a path segment has endpoints and this is not reflected in our model of line as length (or number). Two paths can be joined if and only if the destination of one segment is the source of another. But familiar algebraic operations such as addition are not sensitive to geometry. We can add any number to any other number. These considerations suggest an algebraic model of path with initial point a and end point b in analogy with the ‘function/arrow’ notation $f: A \rightarrow B$ with *domain* A and *codomain* B : the specification of the domain and codomain objects are a necessary part of the structure of the function f . Two functions $p: \mathbf{N} \rightarrow \mathbf{N}$ and $q: \mathbf{N} \rightarrow \mathbf{R}$ are not considered the same even if they are equal at elements since they have different codomain objects. (This is related to the notion of type in logic and computer science. If both p and q are the functions given by squaring numbers, with \mathbf{N} the natural numbers and \mathbf{R} the real numbers, $p(2) = 4$ as natural number whilst $q(2) = 4$ as real number. The images are considered as having different properties in the two situations.)

The composition of functions is geometrically defined to reflect the joining of line segments. Given two functions $f: A \rightarrow B$ and $g: C \rightarrow D$, a composite $fg: A \rightarrow D$ is defined if and only if $C = B$. Here we are constructing algebraic gadgets that resemble geometry. Higher dimensional algebra aims to give a wider class of algebraic tools for modelling geometry, by bringing geometry into the structure of the algebraic operations. A key aspect of this use is its base in and development of methods of category theory.

-FIGURE 2-

An important contribution of category theory and of higher dimensional algebra to science in general is the bringing to the fore and the formalization of ‘process’. In spite of their abundance and importance in all scientific disciplines, processes have been relegated to the background in set- and equation-based mathematics. Consider, for example, a simple equation: $1 + 2 = 3$. What does it mean? The left hand side is same as the right hand side? NO! ‘ $1 + 2$ ’, an expression, is not the same as ‘3’, a number. What we mean to say is that there is a process that takes 1 and 2 as inputs and gives 3 as output, which can be made explicit by rewriting the equation as $1 + 2 \rightarrow 3$. These processes are formalized as arrows $f: A \rightarrow B$. Category theory, which replaces the membership axioms of set theory with axioms on composition of arrows/functions, is the mathematics of processes (Lawvere & Schanuel, 1997). Processes that compose or transform processes can be objectified as 2-dimensional arrows. In general, given objects of level n which ‘fit together’, the process which forms their ‘composition’ is an object of level $n + 1$. From this perspective set theory may be regarded as 0-dimensional, category theory as 1-dimensional algebra and so on.

When we regard set theory and linear symbol string manipulations as the only available means of doing science or mathematics, then we are forced to reduce all complex phenomena and processes to structure-less elements of set theory. This gives rise to lot of dissatisfaction.

In the context of computation, “some of the most crucial distinctions in computing methodology, such as sequential versus parallel, determinate versus nondeterministic, local versus distributed disappear if all one sees in computation is pure symbol pushing”, which is fuelling efforts to enrich and enlarge theories to capture “what really matters” (Aceto, Longo & Victor, 2003). In mathematics, a model of ‘line’ as a collection of points is rather unsatisfactory. But if we objectify a line as a function/arrow or process, then we not only capture its holistic nature but also retain the computational power that has become synonymous with set theoretic reductionism. In this sense the mathematical enterprise of higher dimensional algebra may be termed holistic reductionism. In the present context it is important to note that a golden mean of holism and reductionism has already been identified as the method required to further neuroscience. In the words of Albright and colleagues, “the issue is whether we can succeed in developing new strategies for combining reductionist and holistic approaches in order to provide a meaningful bridge between molecular mechanism and mental processes: a true molecular biology of cognition” (Albright et al., 2000, p. S2). And for Shatz, “the challenge now is how to put the molecules back into cells, and the cells back into the [neural] systems, and systems back into [brain] trying to really understand behaviour and perception” (Gershon, 2001). Category theory and more general higher dimensional algebra provide methods to relate smaller pieces to a bigger whole of which they are a part. For example, (end) points are identity paths; lines or edges are identity squares (Brown & Mosa, 1999). In other words, higher dimensional algebra has already met a challenge similar to the one of integrative neuroscience and hence exemplifies potentially useful methods for understanding the brain.

A key working method refined in category theory is that properties of objects can be formally described in terms of their relations to other objects to be contrasted with a description of an object in terms of its internal constituents. For example, in category theory a

singleton set is described as a set to which there exists only one function from any other set (Lawvere & Schanuel, 1997, p. 213). Whereas in set theory, a singleton set is described in terms of its internal constituents as a set containing one element. In the words of Mac Lane, “Category theory asks of every type of mathematical structure: “What are the morphisms?”; it suggests that these morphisms should be described at the same time as the objects” (Mac Lane, 1998, p. 30). Brain, beginning with the contrast sensitive visual neurons to the pervasive contextual effects in neural representation, perception, and conceptual thinking, appears to employ a similar relational strategy in formulating a description of the world with which it interacts. This is an initial impetus for our study of the brain from category theoretic perspective.

The formal languages of physical and psychological sciences are currently extended to study the brain. In view of our failure to provide a satisfactory coherent scientific account of brain functions, we may need a structured language tailor-made to the unique specifications of the brain- the interface between physical and phenomenal worlds. The importance of and the need to develop structured languages suited to the problems at hand has been recognized in mathematical sciences beginning with the Greek Euclidean geometry to the more recent monumental conceptual repertoire built by Alexander Grothendieck. Category theory and higher dimensional algebra provide new languages required to capture and clarify many aspects of geometry and topology, and to solve problems and do new calculations. Many of the basic tenets of Gestalt psychology, which found widespread empirical validity, could not be formally expressed in set theoretic language of elementism (Albright et al., 2000). Fortunately, category theory is rich enough to capture these Gestalt principles. Ehresmann and colleagues, in their pioneering category theoretic study of cognition, mathematically captured the key Gestalt principle of ‘whole is greater than the sum of its parts’ using the notion of colimit (Ehresmann & Vanbremeersch, 1987). Colimits allow putting together of a

collection of objects (along with their relations) into an object of higher level without requiring it to be reducible to the lower level objects (Brown, Paton & Porter, 2002). Lawvere's explication of part-whole relationship: "each part is included in the whole in two senses, since each part is both itself and its relationship" and illustration of categorical resources "to express how the collective state will influence the state of each part" (Lawvere, 1994, pp. 53-54) appear to be reminiscent of the Gestalt principle: "the properties of any of the parts are determined by the intrinsic structural laws of the whole" (Gilbert et al., 2000). We now suggest that higher dimensional algebra has many of the features of the formal language that seems to be needed to develop a description of the brain that includes not only photons and action potentials but also percepts, concepts, and emotions. We hope these ideas will stimulate further work on bringing higher dimensional algebra to bear on brain research.

A COHESIVE MODEL OF PERCEPT, CONCEPT, AND EMOTION

Drawing on the insights of higher dimensional algebra, we distil from empirical data a better alternative to the current conception of percept as a 0-dimensional object, a feature list. From a formal viewpoint, the question 'what are percepts (concepts, emotions)?' is like the old problem with points and lines, etc. The Greeks attempted to *define* points and lines, and then express basic postulates and axioms for these. We now take the axiomatic method as not needing to know what are points and lines, but instead the structure and the axioms give the relations we need to know between these undefined objects, points and lines. The advantage of this abstract method is that the geometry can apply to many more situations than perhaps originally envisaged. We use this very method in formalizing the notions of percept, concept, and emotion.

Gestalt psychologists brought the holistic nature of percept into sharp focus (Albright et al., 2000; Kandel & Wurtz, 2000). They forcefully argued that percepts could not be reduced to

collections of sensory elements. According to Gestalt theory, percept is organizing sensations. This immediately suggests an alternative to the current objectification of percept as a set, a feature list. Percept is not a 0-dimensional object but is a process, a process of composing or putting together of sensations. Percept is not a result of the binding of sensory features but is the very process of binding. This paradigm shift can be discerned in Singer's investigations of the binding problem. Drawing on Singer's studies, Kandel and colleagues explicitly state that, "binding of visual attributes is tantamount to their reaching the perceiver's awareness" (Albright et al., 2000, p. S37). To put it more clearly, in the words of Stanislaw Ulam, "you always perceive a function, never an object in the set-theoretic or physical sense" (Rota, 1997, pp. 57-59). Percept, the process of composing sensation, can be objectified as a function/arrow $p: A \rightarrow B$ (Figure 3). Perception is not a photocopy of physical stimuli and yet it is stimulus-driven. On an abstract level, perception is a higher dimensional object compared to sensory stimulus. If we compare sensation to data points, percept is a model or a curve that brain fits to the data, which conforms to the Gestalt viewpoint of perception being constructive.

Careful examination of the relation between percepts and concepts in the context of the Dalmatian image designed by R. C. James (Miller, 1999) suggests a model for concepts. Most of us when we look at the image for the first time perceive black patches of various shapes and sizes on white background. But once we are told that there is a Dalmatian, we immediately perceive it. Conceptual knowledge such as DALMATIAN is, thus, a process that transforms the percept of 'black patches on white background' into the percept of 'Dalmatian'. Concept, the process of transforming percepts, which are themselves processes, is modelled as a 2-dimensional arrow $c: p \Rightarrow q$ (Figure 3e). In general, given two percepts, we need a contrivance to compare them. Just as mathematicians invented function as a device to compare sets, evolution appears to have come up with a means, i.e., concept to compare

percepts. Concept provides a comparison of percepts. Empirical support for this notion of concept as a classificatory device of percepts comes from the fact that we use concepts to categorize our perceptual experiences. The 2-dimensional arrow model of concept draws on the mathematical experience where comparison between objects is a function/arrow and if the objects that are compared are themselves arrows then the comparison is a higher dimensional arrow (Brown & Porter, 2002b).

Extending the above line of reasoning suggests a model for emotions. Consider the trolley dilemma, a paradox of moral reasoning that has been puzzling philosophers for ages (Helmuth, 2001). Here subjects say it's ok to switch the tracks of a train which is speeding down to meet with a disaster and would kill all five passengers aboard even if switching the tracks kills a person. The rationale appears to be that there is a net saving of 4 lives. But subjects say it's not ok to push a person onto the tracks of the train to stop the train and thereby save the same 5 lives at the cost of one life. When the situation is modelled in terms of numbers, in both cases we have $5 - 1 = 4$ lives saved. The paradox is 'how is it that the subjects reason differently when the scenario ' $5 - 1 = 4$ ' is the same?' A comparison to a simple mathematical problem clarifies the situation. From the volume measurements (numbers) of a sphere and a cube we may not discern their differences. But we can clearly see their differences once we climb up the dimensional ladder. Similarly the differences in the thinking that led to different decisions cannot be discerned at the level of mere numbers. The difference is in the associated higher dimensional emotions. The emotion associated with the act of pushing a fellow human being to death with one's hands changes the way we think about stopping the train and saving the passengers. This suggests emotion as a process of changing one way of thinking into another way of thinking (Figure 3f). Our model is consistent with Damasio's work on emotions, which shows that emotions structure our thought processes and reasoning (Damasio, 1994), and with the large body of work on the

framing of decisions (Tversky & Kahneman, 1981). Our thinking changes the way we perceive the world and our emotions change the way we think.

-FIGURE 3-

From a formal viewpoint, the hierarchical nature of various brain functions (percept, concept, and emotion) has much in common with the notion of categorification (Baez & Dolan, 1998). In categorification, a lower dimensional algebraic structure is part of a higher dimensional structure. A simple example is ‘sets are identity functions’. Another example is lines or edges can be treated as identity squares (Brown & Mosa, 1999). One key method of categorification is replacing equality with isomorphism. Using this categorification method, given the laws (properties) of a level, we can deduce some operations (structure) of higher level. In our context, this suggests we can obtain the structure of thought by categorifying the properties of perception. Or in other words, we might obtain the laws of perception by decategorifying the operations of thought. Similarly categorifying the laws of thought may give us the operations of emotion.

NEURAL CORRELATES OF CONSCIOUSNESS

Identification and characterization of neural correlates of conscious percepts is currently one of the most actively investigated research topics in cognitive neuroscience. Many experimental investigations presuppose that the neural correlate of percepts and imagery is a brain state. In the words of Rees and colleagues, “A neural correlate of consciousness is a specific pattern of brain activity that correlates with particular conscious experiences” (Rees, Kreiman & Koch, 2002). This assumption appears to be a consequence of the model of percept as an object (0-dimensional feature-list) in the sense we (reasonably) expect the object which has same length as that of a given line to be another line and not a point or some

other object of different dimension. Given our model of percept as a process of composing sensation, we suggest transformation of one neural activation pattern into another pattern of neural activity is likely to correlate better with percepts compared to any single state of a neural network (Figure 4). Our suggestion is in accord with the recent studies of functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) of brain, which show that the fMRI signal is reflective of “intracortical processing of a given area rather than its spiking output” (Logothetis et al., 2001), and with additional findings of ‘process code’ of conscious vision (ffytche, 2002). In addition to percepts, the search is on to find the neural correlates of thinking and imagery (Kosslyn, Ganis & Thompson, 2001). Based on our model of concept as a higher dimensional process compared to percept, we suggest that the process of transforming the processes of transforming neural activation patterns is likely to correlate better with conceptual thinking than any brain states. Similarly, emotions are likely to correlate better with further higher order neural processes compared to any brain state. The main point of this exercise is to show that the higher dimensional models that we have uncovered do readily admit neurobiological interpretation.

-FIGURE 4-

More importantly, we think of brain as a nothing more than its state, i.e., a collection of neurons and their corresponding activities such as firing or rest. As a result of which we try to account for all brain functions (percepts, concepts, emotions...) in terms of various neural network states. This strategy is analogous to treating space as a collection of points and modelling algebraically as in point-set topology. But one could obtain more detailed models by considering paths between points, 2-dimensional paths between paths, 3-dimensional paths between 2-dimensional paths and so on in addition to points as has been suggested by Grothendieck (1983). We can implement a similar program with regard to brain space- the

space of all possible brain states. In addition to the states of the brain, we take into account neural process that transform one brain state into another, and processes that transform neural processes, and so on. When we take such a higher dimensional viewpoint to brain, we expect that it would be easy to account for the intricate structure of various brain functions compared to when we try to account in terms of brain states only.

We can extend this line of thought to neural network computation. Currently computation in neural networks is state-based. Memories are states of the network represented as points in the network state space (Figure 4c). We suggest replacing the state-based computation with process-based computation will give rise to richer computational systems. A simple illustration follows. A binary neural network with 2 neurons has a maximum storage capacity of 4 memories corresponding to its 4 states (00, 01, 10, 11). If we use the state-transitions of the same network to represent memories, we can store 16 memories (00 \rightarrow 00, 00 \rightarrow 01, 00 \rightarrow 10, 00 \rightarrow 11, ..., 11 \rightarrow 11). One of the major advantages of the process-based neural network computation is that unlike states or points, state transitions or paths can be composed (Figure 4d). Neural network computations are essentially classification and categorization of state-space. We can do classification and categorization in path-based neural networks using the homotopy theoretic notion of deformation (Brown, 1989). Technically speaking, states are identity processes and hence this approach can be regarded as a generalization of the current neural network paradigm (Hertz, Krogh & Palmer, 1991).

FORM-ADDRESSED MEMORIES

Memories in our desktop computers have two attributes: content and location. We have to specify the location of a memory in order to retrieve the contents stored in the memory. Neural networks brought about a paradigm shift by unifying the ‘what’ and ‘where’ of memory, by storing memories in a space of memories. Memory space is constructed as part

of memorizing such that where a particular memory is to be placed in the memory space is specified by the memory's contents. Here the contents of the memory determine its address just as the location of an n -tuple $v = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n)$ in n -dimensional space is determined by its contents v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n . These content-addressable memories of neural networks are undoubtedly a technological advance, but the underlying notion of describing an object by listing its contents, unfortunately, fails to accord with the contextual and holistic nature of memory. Contextuality means 'what an object is' is determined by 'where it is' and not by 'what it contains'. More importantly, an object cannot be described by listing its contents because in holistic description the object has no contents; it has form or structure. For example, when we read a novel we remember the gist or summary of the story, though we may have trouble recollecting the exact sequence of sentences and words in the novel. Our memories are not photocopies and remembering is not reading off from the photocopy instead of the original (Bartlett, 1932; Neisser, 1967). Our memory of the story is more like a form or structure of the story. When we retrieve or recollect the information that is in our memory, we are representing the form in words just as an artist builds a sculpture of an object she has seen earlier in the medium of her choice. The notion of memory as form or the holistic and constructive nature of memory has recently been brought into sharp focus (Schacter, 1996; Schacter, Norman & Koutstaal, 1998; Kandel, Kupfermann & Iverson, 2000).

In neural networks information is represented as a feature list and eventually in terms of bits, strings of 0s and 1s. An example, dog = [1 0 1] with 1 denoting the presence of a feature such as 'tail' and 0 denoting the absence of a feature. According to this model, we recognize a stimulus as a 'dog' by comparing features in the stimulus with the corresponding features in the memory, i.e., using a bit-wise computation. This model is inconsistent with the results of experimental investigations of visual object recognition and scene categorization, which

clearly show that our visual system is capable of recognizing objects without necessarily recognizing their features or contents (Marshall & Halligan, 1995; Vuilleumier & Landis, 1998; Li, VanRullen, Koch & Perona, 2002; Rasche & Koch, 2002; Rousselet, Farbe-Thorpe & Thorpe, 2002). Here it is important to distinguish form of an object from subsets (contents or parts or features) of the object. For example, when we say circle is the form of disc, circle is not treated as a subset (bunch of points; contents) of the disc but as the relation between object disc and other objects, i.e., background.

To do justice to these experimental findings, we need a mathematical model of the relevant information about a percept or a memory without breaking it into elemental pieces and to represent that information in a way that is amenable to computation. The structure of mathematics gives us a hint. Mathematical objects such as number or group are like percepts in that they are structures or wholes that have no internal contents and all the information about these structures is in their relations to other structures. For example, all the information that there is to know about the number '2' is in its relations to other numbers. Category theory, which models this particular facet of mathematics by asserting that mathematical objects are structures and that structures are observable only through comparison, can provide the necessary tools to develop a theory of neural information processing that accords with experimental data. Taking a cue from category theory, we now develop a model of information storage and retrieval wherein information is not a list of features, but is a unitary whole formally represented as an arrow $f: A \rightarrow B$, with A and B thought of as endpoints integral to the arrow f . We call this memory model 'Form-Addressed Memory', to be contrasted with the content-addressable memories of neural networks. To facilitate comparison, we take the Hopfield model (Hopfield 1982; Hertz, Krogh & Palmer, 1991) and replace the element-wise computations underlying information storage and retrieval with operations defined in terms of arrows and their composition.

We begin with a brief recap of the basic operations of memorization and recognition in Hopfield neural networks. Information to be memorized is represented as a feature vector Y , an $n \times 1$ matrix. Memory W of the vector Y is obtained by multiplying the vector Y with its transpose Y^T , a $1 \times n$ matrix. The weight matrix $W = YY^T$ is an $n \times n$ matrix. If the neural network is stimulated with Y after it memorized Y , the network recognizes the stimulus as Y : $WY = YY^TY = Yb \sim Y$, since $Y^TY = \sum y_i^2 = b$, the scalar product of Y with itself. Moreover, the weight matrix W satisfies $WW = W$. In detail

$$WW = YY^TYY^T = YbY^T = bW \sim W.$$

First, we provide a mathematical description of the feature vector Y without referring to its internal contents, the elements y_i . Such a description may be treated as holistic. In the category of matrices, an $u \times v$ matrix Z can be represented as an arrow $Z: u \rightarrow v$ (Mac Lane, 1998, p. 11). Matrix multiplication is given by composition of arrows subject to the condition that two arrows can be composed if and only if the target of one arrow is same as the source of the second. The feature vector Y is represented as an arrow $Y: n \rightarrow 1$ and its transpose Y^T as an arrow in the opposite direction $Y^T: 1 \rightarrow n$. Memorizing Y corresponds to composing Y with its opposite Y^T . Memory, $W = Y \circ Y^T: n \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow n = n \rightarrow n$, where ‘o’ denotes composition of arrows (Figure 5). In our model, memory W is an idempotent endomap, i.e., $W \circ W = W$ and $Y^T \circ Y = I: 1 \rightarrow 1$, an identity arrow. Given these properties, we can readily show that if we present the information that was memorized, i.e., Y as stimulus, the memory model will recognize the stimulus as Y , i.e., $W \circ Y = Y$. In detail

$$W \circ Y = n \rightarrow n \rightarrow 1 = n \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow n \rightarrow 1 = n \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 1 = n \rightarrow 1 = Y.$$

-FIGURE 5-

In terms of neurobiology, synaptic strength w_{ij} is simply a concise notation for describing pre- and post-synaptic neurons’ activities x_i and x_j . In other words, when we say synaptic

strength increased, we are simply saying that the number of receptors on the post-synaptic neuron or the amount of transmitter released by pre-synaptic neuron has increased. Along the same lines, we can think of a means to describe weight matrix W i.e., all the synaptic weights w_{ij} , w_{pq} , etc., as a single object. Our description of the weight matrix W as an idempotent endomap $W: n \rightarrow n$ does just that.

Form-addressed memories bring out a key principle of neural information processing. In general terms, neural information processing is ‘construction and composition of opposites’. In the case of our memory model, neural processing underlying memorization of a percept consists of composing the percept (an arrow, $f: A \rightarrow B$) with its opposite ($g: B \rightarrow A$) constructed from the given percept. In neural networks, when a feature vector is memorized, the vector is composed (multiplied) with its opposite (transpose). These principles appear to be applicable to neural processing underlying perception also.

The parallels between percept and memory, in cognitive terms, have been recognized: “memory ... is a constructive process like sensory perception” (Kandel, Kupfermann & Iverson, 2000, p. 1239). This similarity holds even when we go down to the neurobiological details and clarifies what exactly we mean by “visual perception is a creative process” (Kandel & Wurtz, 2000, p. 492). Beginning with Hartline’s discovery of contrast sensitive neurons to the relatively recent work of Hubel and Wiesel, we know that neurons detect change or contrast or boundaries (Albright et al., 2000). If edges or borders are the only sensory information available to the brain, then how do we see surfaces? Our perceptual world is not that of outlines. This puzzling feature of perception has been noted by Hubel: “Many people, including myself, still have trouble accepting the idea that the interior of a form ... does not itself excite cells in our brain, ... that our awareness of the interior as black or white ... depends only on cell’s sensitivity to the borders” (Wurtz & Kandel, 2000, p. 537). What is the nature of neural information processing that the brain applies to sensation to

generate percepts? Here again the brain takes sensation (change or contours) and composes with its opposite (constant or surface) to give rise to the percept of visual objects with their smooth surfaces and well-defined boundaries (e.g. computer in front of you). The notion that brain constructs percepts by composing sensation with its opposite is related to the current conceptualisation of visual processing in terms of boundary and surface systems (Grossberg & Mingolla, 1985a, b; Rogers-Ramachandran & Ramachandran, 1998; Lamme, Rodriguez-Rodriguez & Spekreijse, 1999; Grossberg, 2000). A key difference being instead of thinking of brain as filling in point-by-point inside the outlines to obtain a percept, which cannot accommodate the experimental findings on afterimages (Shimojo, Kamitani & Nishida, 2001), we suggest that brain, given sensation, constructs the opposite of sensation and composes it with sensation to generate the percept (Figure 6).

-FIGURE 6-

The form-addressed memory is a generalization of the current neural network paradigm. In form-addressed memories, unlike the case of neural networks, the information to be stored and retrieved need not be a vector. The formal operations of storage and retrieval in form-addressed memories can be applied to higher dimensional information by replacing arrows with higher dimensional data structures such as 'squares' or 'cubes'. The main motivation for developing form-addressed memories is to enable memory computations with various higher dimensional structures encountered in cognitive neuroscience. In addition to the memories of perceptual information that we have modelled, we have memories of sensation, concepts, and emotions (Neisser, 1967; LeDoux, 1996; Schacter & Buckner, 1998; Tulving, 2000). Empirically speaking, sensation, percept, concept, and emotion are clearly different from one another, but it has not been possible to distinguish them formally. Percepts and concepts are all represented as feature lists (Fodor, 1998). Sensory, perceptual, conceptual, and emotional

information constitute a hierarchy corresponding to that of points, lines, squares, and cubes, respectively as shown earlier. To calculate with these formal cognitive objects, the algebra of points (set theory) is not good enough. We need higher dimensional algebra: algebra of lines (or category theory), algebra of squares, cubes and so on.

It has long been recognized that the unit of learning and memory is a pattern (Grossberg, 1978). Nevertheless the current neural network computations of pattern recognition, in view of the fact that they are based on computing dot product or hamming distance between strings of 0s and 1s, are not really recognizing patterns. They are bit-recognition algorithms. In other words, pattern as a unit distinct from bits does never enter into the present-day neural network computations. Our representation of pattern as an arrow and recognition via composition of arrows is true pattern recognition.

BASIC UNIT OF NEURAL INFORMATION

The inadequacy of 0-dimensional descriptions of percept is acutely felt in the study of visual perception: “Clearly, the commonly used low-level descriptions such as orientation, number, and overall intensity of contextual elements are not sufficient to explain the results [on contextual modulation]” (Herzog & Fahle, 2002). Experimental investigations continue to reveal the crudeness of acontextual frameworks (Albright & Stoner, 2002). Contextual interaction is a defining property of perception. Besides the familiar brightness, color, and orientation contrast effects, shape, motion, texture, and size have all been found to interact with one another (Albright et al., 2000; Kandel & Wurtz, 2000), not to mention complex contextual effects such as auditory information influencing visual perception. There have been various neural network models parametrically fine-tuned to fit particular data sets within a given sensory modality, but it is not clear how to generalize the computations across modalities. For instance, how would a model of brightness contrast be generalized to account

for (say) perception of multiple flashes when a single flash is presented along with multiple beeps (Shams, Kamitani & Shimojo, 2000)?

Given that the brain underlies perception, brain provides a concrete general model capable of accounting for all particular contextual effects. Horizontal connections within the cortical layers are thought to mediate contextual influences on visual processing (Gilbert, 1992). In an overview of the central visual pathways, Wurtz & Kandel conclude “thus neural information flows in two directions: [vertically] between layers and horizontally throughout each layer” (Wurtz & Kandel, 2000, p. 545). These neuroanatomical substrates mediating contextual effects suggest that the classical information theoretic notion of bit as the basic unit of information may not be appropriate for investigation of neural information processing underlying perception. We suggest 2-dimensional square as a better model for the basic unit of neural information (Figure 7). Horizontal edges of the square represent horizontal synaptic connections within cortical layers carrying contextual information while vertical edges denote vertical synapses communicating content across layers. We can use the algebraic framework of double categories invented by Ehresmann to calculate with 2-dimensional data structures (Brown & Spencer, 1976; Brown & Mosa, 1999). Since 2-dimensional shapes (squares) are more complex than 1-dimensional shapes (lines), the conditions defining composition in double categories are more detailed. But the resultant algebraic structures are much more general. For example, groups are a special case of groupoids and double groupoids are more ‘non-commutative’ than groupoids (Brown & Porter, 2002a). The relevance of these higher dimensional notions for computation has already been recognized in theoretical computer science (Power, 1995; Gadducci & Montanari, 1999; Gaucher, 2000; Goubault, 2000).

-FIGURE 7-

Connectionism also recognizes the geometry of neural information processing –lateral interactions– and models it in terms of 0-dimensional numbers, i.e., synaptic weights (Grossberg & Mingolla, 1985a, b; Hertz, Krogh & Palmer, 1991). We have already seen that even in the simple case of path segments arrows/functions capture much more geometry than do mere numbers and hence can account for more data. The neural network approach is like characterizing a cube in terms of length, breadth, and width. Our higher dimensional approach, on the other hand, is like abstracting the higher dimensional notion of volume and modelling it explicitly so that we may characterize any arbitrarily shaped solid object. The move from artificial intelligence symbolic computation paradigm to neural networks to our higher dimensional algebraic models can be viewed as a gradual refinement to accommodate more and more of the geometry of neural computations. Modelling both feedforward and lateral information processing in terms of numbers (synaptic weights) fails to accurately reflect the qualitatively distinct functional contributions of vertical and horizontal synapses: content *vs.* context. Our 2-dimensional square model of neural information preserves these distinctions and is a first step towards objectifying context from the standpoint of neuroscientific data. In subsequent studies, drawing upon the experience of translating the Hopfield model into arrow language, we plan to generalize neural network models of contextual influences on visual form perception (Grossberg & Mingolla, 1985a, b) into squares of double categories.

METAPHORS FOR THE BRAIN: PHYSICS *vs.* MATHEMATICS

There are many models in neuroscience, but hardly one viable theory of brain (Stevens, 2000). The problem appears to be not so much with finding answers but with formulating questions. The scenario is all the more confusing if we ask for theories of brain that encompass cognition besides the physics of brain. Inspired by the success of methods that

established physics as an exemplary scientific discipline, cognitive neuroscientists emulate the practices of physical sciences. Physicists begin their elucidation of a given phenomena by asking for underlying causal mechanisms. And cognitive neuroscientists adopt the same strategy to the domain of brain sciences. When faced with a problem such as loss of memory in dementia, cognitive neuroscientist immediately asks ‘what causes memory loss in dementia?’ In the following we motivate the need to formulate and address ‘coherence questions’ before answering the questions of causality.

Let’s begin with a simple illustration of the issues involved. You want to go from USA to India and you have at your disposal a model of the world, which happens to be a list of countries. According to this model, assuming that the list is alphabetically ordered, India is somewhere in the middle, and USA is at the bottom of the world. It is not hard to see the futility of trying to answer ‘how to go from USA to India?’ in terms of this list model. Before we can calculate the path that takes us from USA to India, we need to refine our primitive list model of the world. We do this refinement by asking ‘how or where does India fit with USA?’ or ‘how to put together various countries into a world?’ When formulated as a question of ‘putting together’ or as a question of cohesion, we obtain as a solution a more realistic model of the world, which includes not only countries but also relations between countries or boundaries that specify how countries fit together. Once the question of cohesion is answered, we are in a better position to answer the question of going from one country to another, and drawing parallels to physics, a causal question.

Physical reasoning pervades much of computational neuroscience methodology; it is not merely confined to questions of causality as opposed to that of cohesion. Recognition, for example, is modelled as a minimum energy configuration, so are percepts, memory, decisions... We need to understand the fixation on physics as *the* role model for science so as to ensure that abandoning physical reasoning in thinking about brain functions is not

detrimental to the advancement of brain sciences. The ease of implementation of the methods of physics embodied in measurement has done much to promote the generally accepted view that science is essentially quantification. In the context of the study of concepts it has been argued, quite convincingly, that the mainstream cognitive science has chosen the path of measuring what can be readily measured, i.e., categorization, instead of developing methods to measure what ought to be measured, which is thinking (Fodor, 1998; Solomon, Medin & Lynch, 1999). In the name of science there is a rush to reduce everything including art and aesthetics to measurable quantities such as arousal (Ramachandran & Hirstein, 1999; Wheelwell, 2000) since many scientists believe that objectivity can be found in numbers only. But numbers are just a beginning, a first approximation even in the case of physics (c.f. symmetries modelled as groups or structures). In mathematical sciences it has become abundantly clear that science is not merely a study of numerical quantities but more importantly of structures, which may be thought of as a refinement of the quantitative view of the world. Noether's work on algebraic topology provides a compelling case study: "Noether revolutionized algebraic topology by emphasizing the importance of homology groups. Previous work had focused on Betti numbers, which are just the dimensions of the rational homology groups. Noether noted that if we work with homology groups rather than Betti numbers, we can solve more problems" (Baez & Dolan, 1998, p. 3). Structures such as categories provide a more accurate account of a number of phenomena. From this vantage point we find that science is not reducing qualities to quantities but building algebraic structures that capture quality in a manner amenable to calculations (Lawvere, 1973, pp. iii-v; Baez & Dolan, 2001).

We now show that the terminology of cohesion is not alien to the problems of cognitive neuroscience. Mind, according to the current working description, is a collection of percepts, concepts, emotions, memories... a collection of mental objects or "a set of operations of the

brain” (Kandel, 2000, p. 5), which is reminiscent of modelling the world as a list of countries. In view of the cohesive nature of our subjective experience, it is not too unreasonable to assert that our percepts, thoughts, memories, and feelings are not discrete elements floating in a subjective void. The task in front of us is to replace the list model of mind with a map of mind, which includes not only mental objects but also relations between them.

What is true of mind is also true of memory and many other brain functions. Neural computations mediating various cognitive functions are all organized in a modular fashion. There is the visual cortex processing visual information, there is the auditory cortex processing auditory information, and so on. But this is not to say that auditory perception is independent of visual information processing or vice versa (Shimojo & Shams, 2001; Zatorre, 2001). A powerful illustration of the interactions between different sensory modalities is the classic McGurk effect where what you hear depends on what you see (McGurk & MacDonald, 1976). The need to accommodate integrative actions of the brain within the framework of its modular organization is well recognized: “It is unlikely ... that the neural basis of any cognitive function –thought, memory, perception, and language– will be understood by focussing on one region of the brain without considering the relationship of that region to the others” (Saper, Iverson & Frackowiak, 2000, p. 365).

Coherence questions such as the binding problem and questions of integration do occupy a central position in cognitive neuroscience (Croner & Albright, 1999; Roskies, 1999; Robertson 2003). The Gestalt slogan, “whole is greater than the sum of its parts”, more than anything else calls for a scientific scrutiny of ‘putting together’ of pieces into parts of a whole. But the formal tools with which computational neuroscientists think about putting together are limited to addition and multiplication (Bienenstock & Geman, 1995). Our objective here is to point to various formal devices such as colimit which permit putting together of qualities (objectified as structures) by refining the familiar notion of addition or

putting together of quantities. Ehresmann and colleagues have explicated the relevance of colimits to the problem of binding (Ehresmann & Vanbremeersch, 1987, 1996).

The relevance of colimits can be readily conveyed from the standpoint of the notion of “best”, which underlies many models of cognitive notions including perception, memory, recognition, and decision-making. The most likelihood principle of Helmholtz, Pragnanz or the minimum principle of Gestalt psychology, and the view of rationality as maximizing self-interest are all various cognitive and behavioural instantiations of the notion of best. In Hopfield neural networks, recognition, a best match, is implemented as a ball rolling down the energy gradient over many non-best states to a minimum energy state (Hopfield, 1982). Here the system requires access to all of the many non-maximal states as a part of computing the best in the course of evolving from input stimulus to output category. Enumerating and rank ordering all possible options before making a decision, be it a network, or a brain, or a human being, turns out to be too expensive to be entertained as a general-purpose model as has become all too clear in the study of rationality (c.f. cost-benefit analysis), which in turn led to questions such as ‘are human beings maximizers?’ Equally questionable is the idea that the neural processing underlying perception involves brain evaluating all possible interpretations of the given retinal image to choose the best, not to mention the problems associated with assigning a number to each one of these infinite number of interpretations. Going by the physical metaphor of a ball rolling downhill, it is beyond doubt that for the ball to fall from a height of 5 ft to 3 ft, it has to go through 4 ft. But this Hopfield model is but one exemplification of the process of finding the best or maximum. The notion of maximum has been sufficiently generalized in the mathematical literature beginning with finding the maximum of, say, $\{3, 4, 5\}$ to cases where the maximal element is not part of the given collection (least upper bound) and further to cases where we don’t have to list all possibles to pick the best (least common multiple). In the case of finding the least common multiple of

any two given numbers (say 4, 6), we don't list all common multiples and rank order them before picking the least or best; given two numbers we directly compute the best (12). The mathematical notion that encompasses all these diverse specific examples of best and many more depending on the category under consideration is the notion of colimit (Brown, Paton & Porter, 2002). Thus it appears that colimits, which allow direct computation of best, can be useful in refining models of perception and memory.

Now that we have enough reasons to break free of the physics role model, we need to search for an alternative which can fill the role played by physics to date. Mathematics provides the necessary guidance for cognitive neuroscience. The questions that fuel pure mathematics are questions of cohesion and not questions of causality. Given (say) algebra and geometry, two distinct pieces of mathematics, mathematician asks, 'how do they fit together as parts of mathematics?' An answer to this question, when expressed mathematically, led to higher dimensional algebra (Brown & Porter, 2002a). (This is not to say that there are no causal questions in mathematics. There indeed are many, but they are not of primary interest. One could for example ask 'did group theory cause category theory?' which involves more of a historical analysis rather than a mathematical analysis.) The higher dimensional algebraic experience that the process(es) of putting together depend on the very nature of the objects being put together and that the process of putting together of objects constitutes an object of higher dimension can help comprehend the structures inherent in the hitherto unwieldy cognitive terminology of percept, concept, emotion, memory ... as briefly illustrated in the present paper.

A problem closely related to that of cohesion is that of modular organization *vs.* integrative actions of brain, which can also benefit from drawing upon mathematics. Broadly speaking, in mathematics one finds that in order to provide a unified mathematical account of mathematics one has to categorize the domain of mathematical discourse into categories

(Lawvere & Schanuel, 1997). The theory of categories, which unifies or shows how various pieces of mathematics relate to one another, can help us comprehend the dialectics of localization and globalisation in the brain. Category theory, viewed as a refinement of set theoretic conception of mathematics, has further relevance to neuroscience. Beginning with the influential discovery of orientation-selective neurons, cognitive neuroscience has amassed a huge volume of neural correlates data. There is a neuron that fires for each one of the many conceivable structures: a neuron tuned to grandmother, another to number 4 (Dehaene, 2002)... This state-of-affairs resembles set-theoretic elementism, wherein every mathematical object is a set: 100 is a set, $\sin x$ is another set, and ζ -function is another complicated set (Barr, 1992; Baez, 2001). And it includes problems analogous to those associated with expressing mathematical constructions in terms of elementhood and set membership, which in neuroscience have come to fore largely due to the contextual nature of brain functions: “it is frankly impossible to learn what role the cell [orientation-selective neuron] plays in perception [of orientated line segment] using this [elementism] experimental approach” (Albright et al., 2000, p. S34). The clarification of the practice of mathematics brought about by category theory, by shifting the focus from objects to relations can provide a framework with which we can begin to refine the neural view of brain functions and to glue the neurons into a cohesive brain.

An undercurrent that may be dimly visible is a programme of modelling various notions of cognitive studies in terms of better-understood notions drawn from within the domain of cognitive science in general and mathematics in particular. Given the precision of mathematical notions, this program can be furthered substantially if we can identify analogues of cognitive notions in mathematics to replace the currently popular physical metaphors. First, we can begin with a few primitives such as sensation and express all other cognitive notions in those terms. Defining percept as a composite of sensation and its

opposite, we find that memory is a percept if percepts are taken as sensations (see Form-Addressed Memories section). This is related to the idea of internal categories where one defines various mathematical objects such as groups and monoids in categories such as the category of sets or of groups (Mac Lane, 1998, pp. 267-287). Comparing the problems of cognitive neuroscience with similar problems encountered in mathematics might help us see percepts, concepts, emotions, and many other notions of cognitive studies in a new light. For example, the Kanizsa square is called “illusory” because the enhanced brightness that is perceived globally cannot be reduced to differences in local pixel intensities. By this very token, the earth is “really” flat since locally the earth is flat. This comparison forces the need to see perception as a local-to-global problem, a process of putting together and we hope to bring the techniques developed in higher dimensional algebra to solve local-to-global problems (Brown & Loday, 1987; Brown, 2002) to bear on the study of perception. Ongoing work along these lines led us to put forward mathematics as a metaphor for the brain. We will present a number of similarities between the workings of the brain and the methods of mathematics to substantiate our thesis that mathematics is reflective of the brain and go on to suggest that category theory and higher dimensional algebra that capture the essences of mathematics, can equally well elucidate the methods of the brain.

Consider the following foundational problem in vision. Vision science begins with a classification of percepts as real or illusory depending on whether there is a sensory image element corresponding to the perceptual experience or not, respectively. The study of visual illusions has been extremely useful in explicating the mechanisms of visual perception in general, but has led to a somewhat paradoxical conclusion: illusion is more veridical than reality (Grossberg & Mingolla, 1985a). A similar scenario exists in cognition in general (Kahneman & Tversky, 1996). Given the foundational role of classification in science, there is a pressing need to develop an alternative to this real-illusion classification which while

capturing the “real” vs. “illusion” distinctions and accounting for the utility of the study of what are currently called “illusions” avoids the above paradox. We suggest that perception is a description of the world and “illusions”, unlike “real” percepts, describe percepts and not objects in the world. The study of illusions lends support: Muller-Lyer illusion describes the contextual nature of perception; illusory contours describe the irreducibility of percept to sensory elements or the constructive nature of perception; faces-and-vase illusion describes the choice nature of perception. The description of descriptions of objects in the world when treated as a description of the world looks illusory (has no immediate correspondence in the world). There is an analogous situation in mathematics: illusions correspond to mathematical definitions (e.g. line), which underlie the effectiveness of mathematical descriptions (e.g. length). Line as defined by Euclid (“a line is that which has no breadth”) doesn’t exist in the world, but in the absence of which we wouldn’t be able to measure the lengths of buildings or bridges in the world.

The general process of going from sensation to perception, which is instantiated in different sensory modalities, has been clearly spelled out experimentally. In terms of touch perception, “Tactile information about an object is fragmented by peripheral sensors and must be integrated by the brain” (Gardner & Kandel, 2000, p. 451). This crystal clear English language description by experimentalists is yet to be translated into mathematical language. There is an analogous situation in mathematics which might help formalize the general process by which brain transforms sensation into percepts. Algebraic modelling of space begins with subdivision, a breaking of space into small comprehensible pieces. For example, a line segment is broken into smaller line segments (see Figure 2a). Next we need to algebraically put these pieces together: an ‘algebraic inverse to subdivision’ (Figure 2b). From this algebra we can reconstruct a space, also known as a ‘classifying space’ (Brown & Porter, 2002a). Sensation, whereby the stimulus space is broken into pieces by our sensory

systems (eyes, nose, ears...) due to the finite nature of receptors, may be compared to ‘subdivision’; neural computations that put together these pieces to ‘algebraic inverse to subdivision’; perceptual experience to ‘classifying space’. In mathematics there are a number of local-to-global problems where the general process of breaking objects into pieces, processing of the pieces, and final putting together of the processed pieces is studied with great precision using colimit theorems (Brown, 2002). The mathematical experience gained in working with colimit theorems in the context of local-to-global problems is a rich resource of concrete methods which can be expected to be useful to translate the experimental understanding of sensory-perceptual transformation by the brain into theory.

Many mathematical calculations take the form of opposites (adjoints), a core feature of mathematics made explicit by category theory (c.f. “adjoint functors arise everywhere”; Mac Lane, 1998, p. vii; Marquis, 2001). Interestingly, as we have noted in the section of form-addressed memories, key neural computations underlying perception and memory are also in terms of opposites.

Sensation, percept, and concept make up a hierarchy, with increasing information available as we ascend the hierarchy. We can perceptually distinguish objects that can’t be distinguished in terms of their retinal images and conceptually distinguish objects that are perceptually indistinguishable (e.g. circle vs. zero). Higher dimensional algebra distilled an analogous hierarchical structure of mathematics: sets, arrows, and 2-arrows... (Baez & Dolan, 1998; Brown & Porter, 2002b).

A comprehensive theory of brain calls for a formalism where algebra merges with geometry, since brain underlies both “geometric” percepts and movement, and “algebraic” thoughts and language (Jackendoff, 1999, pp. 5-9). Higher dimensional algebra unifies algebra with geometry. It captures geometry in a form amenable to calculation. Drawing parallels, brain captures the geometry in which we are embedded in a form accessible for

manipulation and comprehension. This suggests higher dimensional algebra as a thinking device to sharpen our models of the brain and calls for adopting structural computation of higher dimensional category theory (Brown, 1994), which is further higher up in the hierarchy of numerical calculations and symbolic computation, where reduction of structured objects to structure-less elements of sets and symbols of equations is not a prerequisite for calculation and deduction, as a neural computation paradigm to frame questions in brain sciences.

We usually think of brain as “some kind of computer” (Sejnowski & Churchland, 1992, p. 7), but except for the hardware-software distinction and the digital *vs.* analog debate, the exact nature of the generalized computations underlying brain functions haven’t been conclusively worked out. Our mathematics metaphor provides with a rich repertoire of parallels to work with and refine our understanding of the workings of the brain.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Many, if not most, terms of cognitive neuroscience vocabulary are loosely described and rarely defined. Definitions and deductions are the vehicles and pathways of scientific progress. We need an algebraic framework within which we can use terms such as concept and percept in a calculational and deductive mode. The impoverished 0-dimensional set theoretic algebra cannot reflect the abundantly rich sights and sounds of our subjective experience. The knowledge that can be satisfactorily objectified in set theory is the world of a primitive organism (say) a photoreceptor bundle. The world as experienced by this organism consists of mere presence or absence of photons. At most it can “know” the total number of photons on its receptor bundle. A little more evolved organism such as bacteria with an adaptive mechanism can not only detect the presence and absence of glutamate molecules but also can “see” concentration gradients and move towards regions of higher concentrations.

As we move up the evolutionary ladder, we come to humans who can see and feel richly structured objects: flowers, melodies, and emotions... In order to objectify our subjective experiences we need an equally evolved formalism. Careful examination of perception specifies a better alternative framework tailor-made for neuroscience. Perception reduces the fluid flux of sensory data to definite and separate objects –tables, chairs, and computers– so that we can move and make our way in the world. In this sense, perception is reduction, but not reduction to structure-less points of set theory. We see structured objects not punctate photons suggesting that the formalism capable of accurately reflecting cognition should be structured reductionism. Higher dimensional algebra does just that. Instead of reducing objects of interest to structure-less points of sets and symbols of equations written on a line, higher dimensional algebra develops algebraic structures that look like the objects of scientific discourse so that we may calculate and deduce. Thus higher dimensional algebra satisfies the minimal criterion expected of a theoretical framework for cognitive neuroscience.

The present article is a programmatic paper: identifying the techniques and illustrating the methods that seem promising to us, building bridges between theory and data, and providing a rudimentary sketch of an axiomatic study of the brain. We hope to have made a reasonable case for higher dimensional algebraic study of the brain.

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FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1. Linear thinking. **a**, Given a 1-dimensional row of dots, we model it with an equation: $1 + 1 + 1 = 3$ dots. **b**, We successfully extend the same strategy to model 2-dimensional objects. We reduce a 2-dimensional array to 1-dimensional symbol string by inventing a new operation- multiplication: $2 \times 3 = 6$ dots (adapted from Baez, 1995). **c**, Conditioned to what Baez calls “linear thinking” we try to model every phenomena and process by reducing them to a concatenation of symbols written along a line and their manipulations. Thus we obtain the model: $\text{face} = \{\text{eyes, nose, mouth}\}$.

Figure 2. Composition defined under geometric conditions. **a**, Representing paths (e.g. Delhi to Amiens) using numbers, we model the journey from Delhi to Bangor via Amiens as $x + y = z$. But within this formalism $y + x$ also equals z . In other words, our theory says that we can go from Delhi to Bangor by first going from Amiens to Bangor and then Delhi to Amiens, which is incompatible with the given geometry. **b**, A better algebraic model of the geometry is not in terms of numbers but in terms of arrows that behave like functions. We represent paths as arrows and impose geometric conditions on composition. Composite $fg: \text{Delhi} \rightarrow \text{Bangor}$ of two paths $f: \text{Delhi} \rightarrow \text{Amiens}$ and $g: \text{Amiens} \rightarrow \text{Bangor}$ is defined if and only if the destination of first path (Amiens) is same as the source of second path (Amiens).

Figure 3. Cube model of percept, concept, and emotion. **a**, This image gives rise to two percepts: planar pinwheel or cube. Metaphorically, the same sensory data can be perceived or modelled as, for example, a straight line (**b**) or a curved line (**c**) depending on whether the theory (concepts) is linear or non-linear, respectively. **d**, Percept as a process (\rightarrow) of

composing sensation. **e**, Concept as a process (\Rightarrow) that transforms one percept (p or ‘black patches on white background’) into another (q or ‘Dalmatian’). Or in terms of the above image, when you think of the planar image as a cube viewed from one of its corner, you see a cube in depth (Fodor, 1975, pp. 182-183). **f**, Emotion as a process of transforming one way of thinking (c) into another way of thinking (d). **g**, Putting it all together we obtain a cube. The edges of the cube denote percepts (1-dimensional arrows), which constitute the source/target of concepts represented as surfaces (2-dimensional arrows). Concepts in turn constitute the source/target of emotions denoted by 3-dimensional arrow.

Figure 4. Neural correlates of conscious percept. **a**, According to the current view, activity of a single neuron or a pattern of activity in a population of neurons is considered as a candidate neural correlate of conscious perception. Within this framework, the neural correlate of a percept (say) apple could be an activation pattern across a neural network shown below the apple. Here filled circles represent neurons that are active and lines represent synaptic connections. **b**, We suggest transformation of one pattern of neural activation into another is going to correlate better with percept than any single activation pattern. **c**, Neural activation pattern correlating with a percept is represented as a point in neural state-space, shown here for 2-neuron network. **d**, In our model, neural correlate is a process represented here as a line segment in state-space. Line segments (processes) can be composed, whereas points (states) cannot be composed. For example, composing line segments denoted by ‘1’ and ‘2’ gives another line segment ‘3’.

Figure 5. Memorization and recognition without bit-wise computations. **a**, Perceptual information Y is depicted as an arrow $Y: n \rightarrow 1$. **b**, Memory W of the percept is formed by composing Y with its opposite Y^T . **c**, Recognition of the stimulus $Y: n \rightarrow 1$ by the memory

$W: n \rightarrow n$ as $Y: n \rightarrow 1$ is represented as a commutative diagram. Commutative diagrams assert the equality of two paths (Y and $Y \circ Y^T \circ Y$) between two points (n and 1).

Figure 6. Construction and composition of opposites. Given sensation, percept is formed by constructing the opposite of sensation and composing it with sensation. Applying a similar process to percept gives the memory of the percept.

Figure 7. Two-dimensional neural information. **a**, Neural information flows in 2 directions: vertically and horizontally. **b**, The 2-dimensional flow of neural information can be modelled as a 2-dimensional process or arrow/function and depicted pictorially as a square. Vertical edges of the square represent source/target with respect to horizontal structure, while horizontal edges denote source/target with respect to vertical structure. **c**, Composition of squares is defined to accord with geometry just as in the case of 1-dimensional algebra. The composite of 4 squares in which each pair of parallel inner edges matches is the same whether one composes first horizontally and then vertically, or first vertically and then horizontally.

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ABSTRACT

Recognizing the limitations of element-wise set-theoretic constructions in accommodating contextual effects in perception, neuroscientists are trying to move beyond elementism. Mathematicians also recognized the shortcomings of 0-dimensional elementism in modelling geometry, which led to the development of higher dimensional algebra. Here we show that higher dimensional algebra meets some of the demands of cognitive neuroscience data and hence may become indispensable in implementing the paradigm shift from acontextual models such as the feature list model of percept and concept to empirically valid models. Drawing upon the experience of higher dimensional algebra, we distil higher dimensional models of percept, concept, emotion, memory, and neural information from experimental data. These studies brought to light a number of parallels between the methods of mathematics and the workings of the brain, which led us to put forward higher dimensional algebra that provides a mathematical model of mathematical practice as a model of the brain.

FIGURE 1

a

b

c

FIGURE 2

FIGURE 3

FIGURE 4

FIGURE 5

a

$$n \xrightarrow{Y} 1$$

b

FIGURE 6

FIGURE 7

a

b

c

Dear Dr. Rayudu,

Your manuscript, "Higher dimensional algebraic Study of Brain Functions", has been read by three experts in the fields of brain science and mathematics. I am afraid that the balance of their assessment of your paper is quite negative. Although Reviewer 1 commends it on attempting the "near-impossible", the problems he identifies (such as setting up a straw man in discussing prior work, obscure notation, lack of definition of mathematical concepts that seem to be key to understanding your thesis) are severe. Reviewers 2 and 3, both eminent mathematicians with decades of experience in theoretical neurosciences, are even more critical both in their evaluation of the manuscript and of the approach it reports, and in their conclusions. Moreover, as a reader who has been trained both in mathematics and in cognitive sciences, I feel that the criticisms leveled by the reviewers are completely justified.

My decision is, therefore, to reject this manuscript. I am sorry that I could not be the bearer of more positive news.

Thank you for considering Cognitive Science as a venue for publishing your work.

Shimon Edelman
Associate Editor, Cognitive Science

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Reviewer #1: Ennio Mingolla

Review of Rayudu et al. " Higer dimensional algebraic . . . "

This manuscript attempts a near-impossible feat - to convince cognitive neuroscientists to consider a formalism that most have never heard of, and to thereby revolutionize brain science. It is easy to be dismissive of such an enterprise - psychology, particularly perceptual psychology, is littered with debris left behind by saviors trumpeting some formalism or other - information theory, Lie algebras, fiber bundles, etc. Although I'm not entirely convinced of the utility of the authors' prescriptions, my review makes a case that their ideas deserve airing. The case is not without reservations; at a minimum, the manuscript needs considerable rewriting. Still, I found myself pausing and thinking at several points in the manuscript, which is more than I can say of most of the more mainstream published papers that I read! The main thrust of this review will thus be to offer some suggestions for rewriting.

My first suggestion is that the authors seriously polish their prose. I surmise that at least two of them are native English speakers, but you would never know that from much of the wording of the text. Many phrases are not idiomatic, and the "flow" of sentences is at times tortuous. E.g., "According to Gestalt theory, percept is organizing sensations." (p.

11) It's one thing to accept such constructions in a straightforward empirical paper, quite another to work through possible parsings in a conceptual piece like the present.

My next suggestion is to organize the paper a bit more aggressively, by putting up front much of the (quite appropriate) critique of elementism and reductionism in current cognitive neuroscience. Yes, much of that does already occur in the early pages, but other parts of that critique occur (or recur) later. The target audience - cognitive neuroscientists ignorant of category theory - is going to need a great deal of motivation, to say the least, to consider something as unfamiliar as what the authors are proposing. They need to make a convincing case that the present trajectory (feature lists, memory as network states, etc.) is entirely hopeless before they will be moved to consider an alternative - especially one that means they'll need to study a new kind of math.

Next, create a more compact, self-contained introduction to those key concepts of category theory that will be used in the paper. (process, codomain, colimit, etc.) The examples in this section should be the simplest ones that introduce the mathematical notions, without any attempt to link to neuroscience. It would be most useful to include a tabular "glossary" section with definitions of key terms, and to highlight in some way one or two of the most elementary possible published introductions to the subject for readers who want to pursue the topic more.

Only then should neuroscience applications of category theory be illustrated. Too often in the course of reading the manuscript I saw a mathematical term first used as a *deus ex machina*: "Ehresmann and colleagues, in their pioneering category theoretic study of cognition, mathematically captured the key Gestalt principle of 'whole is greater than the sum of its parts' using the notion of colimit (Ehresmann & Vanbremeersch, 1987). Colimits allow putting together of a collection of objects (along with their relations) into an object of higher level without requiring it to be reducible to the lower level objects (Brown, Paton & Porter, 2002)." Now, I find the idea that one can capture Gestalt principles mathematically to be exciting. In a perfect world I would stop reading the manuscript right there, rush to my local library to pick up the 1987 publication from a journal I consult very rarely, if ever, and find my scientific outlook transformed. In real life, though, I'm going to fret about deadlines for an impending grant application, overdue grade reports, and other such nonsense, and remain ignorant. The authors simply have to do better if they want to "reach" me. There needs to be a self-contained exegesis of such a critical gem. Instead, the colimit idea lies dormant until page 26, where it makes no more sense (to someone who does not already know about it) than it did in its first incarnation.

Some particulars:

p7, l4 from bottom: I'm not sure what the "and so on" refers to.

p9, bottom: I know no German, but am told by those that do that the Gestalt maxim is better translated as "the whole is different from the sum of its parts." Since this point (repeated on p26) is so central to the authors' case, I'd urge them to research the translation further.

p10: The use of the word "model" in the section heading is odd in the context of the citation of the Stevens (2000) paper that occurs later.

p10, 118: I don't "get" ". . . the structure and . . ."

p11, top: Gibson devoted much of his life to challenging the relationship of sensation and perception that the authors treat as universally held. (Admittedly, it is widely held and may even be the dominant view, but some additional remarks may be warranted here.)

p12, middle: The transition from train deaths to spheres and cubes is not compelling.

p13, first full paragraph: This stuff is vague and not particularly helpful.

p14, top: I did not understand this paragraph, especially the "is in accord with" part. At a more basic level, the significance of the example of Figure 4 is not clear to me. Are all the transformations for brain processes that mean I'm thinking of "apple" the same? If so, I don't see the conceptual gain over just identifying concepts with brain states. If not, how does one know that there's a common transformation underlying the transition from A to B and from A-prime to B-prime? Similarly, in the middle of the next page, while it is obvious that the transitions among all pairs of binary states can store more memories than the 4 pairs themselves, the authors do not even try to suggest a possible neural substrate for coding these transitions. One "obvious" candidate would be to identify the binary states themselves with cell potential (e.g., mean firing rate) and the transitions as matrices of synaptic weights. But if this is all that is meant, we have an entirely conventional statement, and an unlikely motivator for neuroscientists to investigate "homotopy theoretic . . . deformation."

p18: As elementary as this example is, the steps leading to the line just above "-FIGURE 5-" could be described in just a bit more detail. I rather liked this section, in that it seemed the best example of conveying the different "flavor" that is afforded by adopting the advocated view, as opposed to a conventional view.

p19: Who is being quoted with 'construction and composition of opposites'?

p20: Boundaries and surfaces are treated as "complementary" by Grossberg and colleagues. The idea of composing a sensation with its "opposite" does indeed sound related, but the word "opposite" sounds weird in this context. Also, I'm sure that Grossberg and colleagues feel that they can "accommodate the experimental findings" of Shimojo et al., whatever the latter may have said about that prospect.

p21: The first full paragraph seems to be attacking a straw man (Hamming distance). Researchers like Grossberg, indeed virtually all neural modelers, are constantly extolling their approach as one of pattern computation. Even if the present authors are indeed advancing a better notion of "pattern," they need to engage the best that established methods have to offer on this score, not cartoon simplifications, if they want to be taken

seriously. Even as simple an operation as the generation of "end cuts" by Grossberg and Mingolla (1985) is conceived by those authors as a pattern transformation, however distasteful the present authors may find the formalism in which the machinery that performs that transformation is expressed. (If I'm right, it would not be the first time that a relatively novel idea in science has been expressed in a relatively conventional formalism.) Similar points could be made about numerous memory models and other perception models. Likewise at the top of page 23, the authors decry "0-dimensional numbers, i.e. synaptic weights," but neural network researcher think in terms of patterns of weights, vectors or tensors, that code relationships between connections in spatial maps. Once again, it may well be that the authors have a better idea, but they need to compare their idea to the upper bounds of the existing conceptions, not to toy examples.

p25: The section on Noether may be straightforward for mathematicians, but I don't imagine too many of the journal's readers will understand this section without further explication.

p29: The last sentence before the paragraph break summarizes the promise of the present manuscript and its limitations. If the authors could point to evidence supporting a specific empirical prediction that is falsifiable and that is conceptual "natural" within the context of category theory, but unlikely to be derived from other approaches, I think they would find a ready audience. Instead, we have a manifesto of a group searching for allies. Such a call to arms may be worthwhile, but eliciting support in the absence of such compelling predictions is going to be difficult, at best, and the authors need to do a nearly perfect job at just about everything short of providing such a prediction if they want to recruit others to join them.

P36. The caption of Figures 3 is weird in several places. Most troubling is how the words "transform" and "transforming" are used. I'm left wondering whether some neural event is simply being replaced by some other (following) one, or whether there is any more structural relationship intended. In the latter case, what determines what are possible or impossible transformations? How are such transformations coded or carried out in brains?

p38: There is no "W" in the diagram of Figure 5c.

Bottom line: The authors have put together a thoughtful piece, with a nice integrative reference list, that may foster some thought. With suitable revisions, I think their views deserve exposure.

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Reviewer #2: "Higher Dimensional Algebraic Study of Brain Functions." The Review

>>>>I alternate general comments on sections of the paper with specific comments on specific quotes.

>>>>The first few pages set up a straw-man which ill-represents the best of perceptual modeling.

p.3: Currently percepts are modelled as feature collections. For example, percept = {shape, motion, color}. This feature list model is fundamentally flawed.

>>>> There are many models which represent the links between features as well as the features themselves. See Malsburg's Dynamic Link Architecture for just one example.

p.4. In the process of developing a scientific account of various phenomenon and processes we, the scientists, begin with objectification, and represent the objects of scientific discourse as sets.

>>>> Many scientists of course use more structure: vector spaces, differentiable manifolds, etc.

p.6: "Higher dimensional algebra is an algebraic framework where composition is defined under geometric conditions"

>>>> But this is too vague and general to provide useful insight.

>>>> The authors then use many pages to express some basic truisms of category theory.

p.8. "the mathematical enterprise of higher dimensional algebra may be termed holistic reductionism."

>>>> Still vague and general.

p.9. "Ehresmann and colleagues, in their pioneering category theoretic study of cognition, mathematically captured the key Gestalt principle of 'whole is greater than the sum of its parts' using the notion of colimit"

>>>>This is meaningless to readers who do not already know category theory! And we still have not been given a formal definition of higher dimensional algebra which the authors repeatedly claim to be the key to their theory. The quotes above from pp. 6 and 8 are hardly specific!

>>>>Motivated by the last paragraph, I used "Find Again" to see where "higher dimensional algebra" is defined. It isn't!! On p.28, I still have not found a definition but instead find:

p.28: "The higher dimensional algebraic experience that the process(es) of putting together depend on the very nature of the objects being put together and that the process of putting together of objects constitutes an object of higher dimension can help comprehend the structures inherent in the hitherto unwieldy cognitive terminology of percept, concept, emotion, memory"

>>>>The manuscript is a waste of time. By page 28, the key notion of the paper is undefined, no mathematics has been done, and we have assertions like this from p.28 that look like bad philosophy rather than good cognitive science. I have no confidence that the authors understand the current status of studies of perception, whether empirical or theoretical.

>>>>Finally, speaking as someone widely published in both cognitive science and category theory, I can add that the authors have not only failed to contribute to the study of perception (or concept, emotion, memory) but also have failed to provide any real insight into category theory or higher dimensional algebra.

>>>>Recommendation: Reject with recommendation never to resubmit.

=====
Reviewer #3:

This manuscript looks like word salad to me: forcing vague excessively abstract mathematical ideas on difficult issues of psychology and cognition. I don't want to get involved with it.

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